

Review Article

Climate Change, Effects and Adaptation Strategies; Implication for Agricultural Extension System in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Tackling climate change is one of the biggest challenges this generation faces. African countries, Nigeria inclusive are particularly vulnerable to climate change because of their dependence on rain fed agriculture, high levels of poverty, low levels of human and physical capital, inequitable land distribution and poor infrastructure. Generally climate change is already affecting agricultural activities with the most devastating adverse effects in Nigeria as: extreme weather condition, frequent drought, increased environmental damage, increased infestation of crops by pests and diseases, depletion of household assets, increased biodiversity loss, depletion of wildlife and other natural resource base, changes in the vegetation type, decline in forest resources, decline in soil conditions, increased health risks and the spread of infectious diseases changing livelihood systems. These conditions emanating from climate change are bound to militate against agricultural production (crop, livestock forest and fishery resources), nutritional and health statuses and the general livelihood activity of the people. Therefore building up resilience and developing adaptation strategies becomes very important if agricultural production in the country will experience any boost. This paper concludes that the agricultural Extension system in the country need to generally revisit its role and in particular the role of the Extension agents. This is very important since the challenge of climate change if neglected will surely render the effort of increasing food production through the dissemination of technical information fruitless.

Keywords: Climate change, effects, adaptation strategies, implications and Agricultural Extension system

INTRODUCTION

Climate change refers to all changes in climate be it as a result of human activities or natural variations. The earth is surrounded by a layer of gases that act like the glass wall (earth's blanket) and ceiling of a green house. These so-called green house gases are necessary to sustain life on earth. They let the sun's rays enter but stop much of the heat from escaping, keeping the planet warm enough to allow life. The problem that we face today is that the blanket of greenhouse gases that occurs naturally in the troposphere is quickly getting thicker as a result of increase emissions of green house gases and this result in the rapid warming of the world's climate. Over the past 100 years, the earth's average surface temperature has risen by around 0.74°C (Direct Gov., 2010). Most scientists agree that global temperature will rise further (by how much depends on future emissions of green house gases) and if the temperature rise is high, changes are likely to be so extreme that it will be difficult to cope with them. There are likely to be more instance and frequent extreme weather events, like floods and hurricanes, and sea levels could rise further. The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) says that human activities are the main cause of the changes seen in climate (Direct Gov., 2010). This, it does in three major ways; burning of fossil fuels, deforestation and growing world population.

Nigeria like all the countries of sub-Saharan Africa is highly vulnerable to the impacts of climate change (NEST, 2004, IPCC 2007 and Apata et. al., 2009). Though climate change is a threat to agriculture and non-agricultural socio-economic development, agricultural production activities are generally more vulnerable to climate change than other sectors, (Kurukulasuriya, et. al., 2006). This is because agricultural production in most sub-saharan African countries (Nigeria inclusive) is dependent on whether and climate. Analysis of 9000 farmers in 11 African countries predicted a fall in farm revenues with current climate scenarios, (Ole et. al., 2009). Butt et al, (2005) went further to predict future economic losses and increase risk of hunger due to climate change. It is stark clear that the combination of high climatic variability, poor infrastructure and a range of other problems associated with climate variability will constitute important challenges for African countries and Nigeria in particular. Smith and Skinner (2002) asserted that climate plays a dominant role in agriculture having a direct impact on the productivity of physical production factors, for example the soil's moisture and fertility. Adverse climate effects can influence farming outputs at any stage from cultivation through the final harvest. Even if there

is sufficient rain, its irregularity can affect yields adversely if rains fail to arrive during the crucial growing stage of the crops (Mowa and Lambi, 2006, Rudolf and Hermann 2009).

In Nigeria, the agricultural sector is the mainstay of the economy though her development funds at present derive more from petroleum oil and gas exploitation. Estimates in 1991 population census indicated that 69% of Nigeria's population was engaged in agricultural activities and the sector contributes about 40% to the nation's Gross domestic product.

In view of the fact that stability and sustainability of sufficient food production in the agricultural sector is the main sure way of eradication poverty and bearing in mind the great threat posed by climate change to the realization of this goal, it becomes very important for the Agricultural system in the country to give climate change issues serious consideration if the objective of increased food production will ever be achieved. This paper seeks to provide answers to disturbing questions like; what is climate change? What causes climate change? What are the effects of climate change? and the implication of climate change to agricultural extension practice in Nigeria.

WHAT IS CLIMATE CHANGE?

Climate change is one of the most outstanding challenges facing the global community and as such has been given different definitions by different authors according to their perception and the way it affects them.

The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) defines climate change as statistically significant variations that persist for an extended period, typically decades or longer. It includes shifts in the frequency and magnitude of sporadic weather events as well as the slow continuous rise in global mean surface temperature. Ozor 2009 defined climate change as change in climate over time, whether due to natural variability or as a result of human activity and is widely recognized as the most serious environmental threat facing our planet today. This definition elicits the seriousness of the threat posed by climate change and the urgency of the need for countries to rise up to this urgent clarion call of combating the negative effects of climate change. The climate we know cannot be said to be static, but variations are very insignificant that it is only climatologists identify it. Over the years, the change becomes more pronounced and significant. This is as a result of earth's natural variations and man's activities which cause emissions of green house gases thereby increasing global warming. This global warming is what actually induces the change in climate.

Scientists have noted that the average temperature of the earth has increased by 0.74 degrees Celsius over the past 100 years. And if nothing is done, there is going to be more rise in the earth's temperature to the extent that it will be difficult to cope with it.

This statement buttresses more the seriousness of the threat pose by climate change to countries that depend mostly on climate-sensitive resources for sustenance of livelihood and overall development. Eboh (2004) stated that countries in sub-saharan African, including Nigeria are likely to suffer the most because of their geographical location, low incomes, low institutional capacity as well as their greater reliance on climate-sensitive renewable natural resources sectors like agriculture. This is further supported by Watson (1997) which stated that African countries are particularly vulnerable to climate change because of their dependency on rain fed agriculture, high levels of poverty, low levels of human and physical capital, inequitable land distribution and poor infrastructure. Adaptation to climate risks in Nigeria is therefore a primary necessity. Government need to integrate climate change issues as well as adaptation strategies into the countries development plan as the climate change risks is not only a challenge to agriculture development (food security) but to the country's general development and livelihood sustenance of the entire citizenry.

CAUSES OF CLIMATE CHANGE

There are four major causes of climate change namely; astronomical causes, volcanic eruptions, variations in solar output and changes in earth's environment as a result of human activity. The intergovernmental panel on climate change (IPCC) says that human activity is the main cause of the changes seen in climate. This it does through activities that cause emissions of greenhouse gases (mainly consist of carbon dioxide, water vapour, methane and nitrous oxide). Studies of long-termed climate change have discovered a connection between the concentrations of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere and mean global temperature. Carbon dioxide is one of the more important gases responsible for the green house effect. These green house gases are able to alter the energy balance of the earth by being able to absorb long wave radiation emitted from the earth's surface. The net result of this process and the re-emission of long wave back to the earth's surface increases the quantity of heat energy in the earth's climatic system. Human activity is changing the amount of green house gases in the atmosphere in three important ways, namely;

1. Burning fossil fuels,

Carbon dioxide is one of the main green house gases and contributors to the green house effect. When fossil fuels like coal, oil and gas burn they release green house gases. Anyadike, (2009) stated that through energy

creating activities like heating homes and building, transportation and cooking food, traveling (for example, by car, plane, bus and train), treating water to make it drinkable, heating it and piping it into homes, manufacturing from fridges, gas flaring, bush burning etc people induce the emission of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere. Since the industrial revolution which began in the 18th century, the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere has increased by 35%. The Niger Delta region of Nigeria is reported to have over one hundred and twenty three gas flaring sites making Nigeria one of the highest emitters of greenhouse gases in Africa (Akinro et al.2008). A recent study by the World Bank (2008) revealed that Nigeria accounts for roughly one-sixth of worldwide gas flaring, Nigeria flares about 75% of her gas. The flares have apparently contributed more greenhouse gases hence climate change in the country.

2. Deforestation

Deforestation where forests are cut down faster than they are replaced is a major contributor to climate change. This accounts for 20 percent of the world's carbon emissions (more than the entire transport sector produces). Deforestation makes such a huge contribution to carbon emissions because trees absorb CO₂ as they grow. If there are fewer trees left to absorb CO₂, then CO₂ will build up in the atmosphere. The agriculture and industry that replace the forests do not only damage the earth's ability to absorb CO₂, they often cause an additional problem by producing carbon emissions of their own. In Nigeria, the primary tropical forest cover has been decimated by 97% mostly since 1990. The remainder is supposedly protected in Cross Rivers National Park and by a two year logging ban imposed in November 2008. The country's broader forest cover was estimated at just over 12% in 2005, being depleted at a rate of 3.3% per annum. The main cause is the demand for wood fuel. Therefore there is need for the country to educate its citizenry on the importance of the forest reserves as well as the need to avoid unnecessary cutting down of trees.

3. A Growing World Population

As the world's population grows, there are more people who need food, livestock and energy. This increased demand leads to increased emissions.

EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

Globally, extreme weather is predicted to become more common and animals, plants and crops are all expected to be badly affected. In Nigeria the effects of climate change is expected not to stop at just effecting the crops and plants (i.e the farmers), it will surely effect the lives and overall development of country. Eboh 2009 stated that the effects of climate change are projected to manifest through changes in land and water regimes, specifically, changes in the frequency and intensity of droughts, flooding, water shortages, worsening of droughts, worsening soil conditions, desertification, disease and pest outbreaks on crops and livestock. Anyadike (2009) stated that the general environmental effects of climate change include; rise in sea level due to melting of ice caps; changes in dates of onset and end of the rainy season; reduced rainfall amounts in some areas and increased rainfall amounts in others, leading to flooding and increase in intensity of atmospheric disturbances such as thunderstorms and line squalls. He went further to state that climate change will deepen poverty both directly and indirectly. The direct impact he explained will manifest through the loss of lives, livelihoods, assets, infrastructure, e.t.c from climate extreme events. Ozor (2009) in listing the impact climate change on national development of the country stated that variations in climate change have led to devastating consequences and effects in various parts of the country which include flooding, desertification, erosion, drought, sea level rise, heat stress, pests and diseases, erratic rainfall patterns and land degradation, specifically he stated that the Southsouth geopolitical zone is mainly affected by sea level rise and deforestation-induced changes; the Southwest zone also is affected by sea level rise and deforestation-induced changes; Southeast by erosion, flooding and land degradation; North-central by changes due to de-vegetation and overgrazing; Northeast by drought, desertification and heat stress; and Northwest also by drought an, desertification and heat stress. The Third assessment report of IPCC (2001) stated that the poorest countries are more vulnerable to the risk of climate change and went further to identify a range of poverty-related climate change impacts as follows; reductions in crop yield(fall in agricultural productivity) in most tropical and subtropical regions due to decreased rainfall, changes in food security, employment, incomes and economic growth, displacement of people from coastal and densely populated low lying areas, salinisation of these fertile areas, exposure of millions of people to new health risks, especially from vector-based diseases like malaria and schistosomiasis, as well as water-borne diseases like cholera and dysentery and malnutrition from the reduction in crop yields .

In Nigeria, though the impact of climate change is already significant the long run impact will be disastrous if nothing is done now to build up the country's resilience against the threat pose by climate change. The impacts of climate change will surely be felt in almost all the geographical location as well as sectors of the nation's development. Specifically it will manifest in the following ways;

1. Crop and animal production

As temperature increases and rainfall pattern becomes more unpredictable, crop yields are expected to drop significantly. Also extreme weather events such as thunderstorms, heavy winds and floods devastate farmlands and can lead to crop failure. Pests and diseases migrate in response to climate changes and variations. It is estimated that by 2100, Nigeria and other West African countries are likely to have agricultural losses of up to 4% of GDP due to climate change (Mendelson, et al 2000). Parts of the country that experienced soil erosion and operate rain fed agriculture could have decline in agricultural yield of up to 50% between 2000 – 2020 due to increasing impact of climate change (Agoumi, 2003; IPCC 2007).

Mowa and Lambi (2006); Rudolf and Hermann (2009) stated that even if there is sufficient rain, its irregularity can affect yields adversely if rain fails to arrive during the crucial growing stage of the crops. Also extreme weather leads to drying up of streams which are sources of irrigation water used by farmers during dry season crop production. Anyanwu (2008) in studying the farmer's perception of impact of climate change on food crop production in Ogbomosho Agricultural zone of Oyo State identified the significant effects of climate change on crop production as; low yield of crop, stunted growth of crop, ease spread of pest and disease attack on crops, drying of seedling after germination and ineffectiveness of agricultural chemicals due to delay of rainfall. This agrees with the statement of Ozor (2009) that variations in rainfall pattern will affect crop production in varying ways depending on the location. He also went further to explain that changes in crop development and phenology as a result of climate change can cause shortening or lengthening of crop cycles that could lead to decreases or increases in productivity. Structural changes he said especially in carbohydrate status of plants can also occur. These changes when they occur will surely affect the nutritional value, taste and storage quality of some fruits and vegetables. Also increases in CO₂ can also lower crop water requirements by reducing transpiration per unit leaf area.

On the side of Livestock production, Ozor (2009) stated that livestock production systems in Nigeria would be vulnerable to climate change in respect of anticipated decrease in rainfall in the Sudan-sahelian zone and consequent reduction in the available pastureland. This he explained further by listing the various ways the anticipated decrease in rainfall will affect livestock as declining availability of surface water resources for animals, possible increase in salinity at water resources for animals, possible increase in salinity at watering points due to increase in temperature and evaporation in the face of reduced rainfall.

This is to say that further changes in rainfall and temperature will affect livestock production as well as availability of animal species. Some species might be unable to adapt quickly enough and habitats might not be available for them to move into. If global temperatures rise by 2 degrees Celsius, 30 percent of all land-living species may be threatened by an increase risk of extinction. Though increase in temperature is generally seen to be destructive to the production of crops and human lives, FAO (2009) noted that livestock production could be boosted by temperature increase. Conversely, Deressa and Hassan (2009) found increasing temperature damaging to the Ethiopian agriculture; a situation that is not uniformly distributed across agro-ecological zones. Issa (2009) in agreement with the findings of Deressa and Hassan (2009) reported that commercial Livestock producers are negatively affected by rising temperature. This is to say that varying climate has varying effects on crops and livestock depending on the agro-ecological location.

2. Fishery.

Fish farming and the associated processes are becoming an important source of revenue and employment in Nigeria. Ozor (2009) stated that subtle changes in key environment variables such as temperature, salinity, wind speed and direction, ocean currents, strength of upwelling due to climate change could sharply alter the abundance, distribution and availability of fish production in the country. In the same vein, African Action (2009) stated that changes in ocean dynamics could lead to changes in migrating patterns of fish and possibly reduced fish landings especially in coastal fisheries. All these will directly and indirectly affect the livelihoods of fish farmers, their immediate families and their dependants. It will also affect the revenue sustenance of those who work or trade on fishery resources. Tubiello (2008) noted three major pathways through which climate change will affect fisheries and aquaculture, as well as dependent communities and their economic activities as;

- Physical and chemical changes in oceans and fresh waters, including increase in water temperature and changes in salinity among others.
- Change in fish production, catch composition and species distribution resulting from a complex interplay of ecological changes and
- Physical changes to coasts, estuaries, wetlands, lakes and rivers caused by changing weather patterns, weather-driven natural disasters and sea-level rise. Fishery resources are known to be highly sensitive to marine environmental changes. Though they had always coped with these changes, future climate changes will likely be so extreme that it may be difficult for them to cope with. Therefore, identification of proper adaptation strategies is a high priority for the fishery sector.

3. Forestry.

The forest reserves of the nation are not left out in the threat posed by climate change. Francesco, (2008) stated that climate change will affect agriculture and forestry through higher temperatures, elevated CO_2 concentration, precipitation changes, increased weeds, pests and disease pressure, and increased vulnerability of organic carbon pools. It is worthy to note that eleven out of the thirty-six states in the country referred to as the frontline states are gradually being swallowed up by desertification. As at 1985, deforestation claimed 1,544sq miles of the nation's forest land. Between 1983 and 1993 alone, Nigeria lost 20% of its forest and woodland areas. Nigeria's primary tropical forest in Cross River State has been decimated by 97%, mostly since 1990. The country's broader forest cover was estimated at just over 12% in 2005, being depleted at a rate of 3.3% per annum. The main cause is the demand for wood fuel. This depletion of the nation's forest reserves when critically looked at is not far from indirect effect of climate change. As a result of the drying up of village or communities forest which the dwellers depend on for firewood, they resort to the depletion of forest reserve as a means of getting wood fuel.

4. Sea levels

Globally, over the past century, the temperature of the atmosphere near the earth's surface has risen by 0.75 degree celcius consequently sea level is expected to rise with the rising temperature, this would swamp some small, low lying islands states and put millions of people in all low-lying areas at risk of flooding.

In Nigeria half of the 15 million population of Lagos lives less than six feet above sea level, including the wealthiest areas of Victoria Island and Lekki Peninsula. Also the Niger Delta may be the source of oil wealth but its low-lying terrain criss-crossed with water ways makes it extremely vulnerable to flooding. Bearing in mind the high population density (9th largest population in the world) of the country any displacement of this mass of people will be catastrophic especially as over 50% of this population lives below poverty lines. Therefore mitigating the impacts of climate change must be given priority if the nations Millennium development goals will ever be achieved.

5. Health of the people.

A healthy nation they say is wealthy nation. Climate change is expected to induce health problems directly and indirectly. The direct effects manifest in persistent and resistant to treatment as were never experienced before. Okhimamhe 2009, in studying the impacts and adaptation of climate change in Northern Nigeria found out that diseases like persistent malaria, hypertension, ulcer, diarrhea, asthma and diabetes are new ailments that were ushered in by the changing climate, with malaria being the most widespread. She pointed out that thirty years ago, the people of the area relied on local herbs for treating illnesses, but now, they have to go to nearby fairly functional clinics for treatment especially because the herbs are no longer able to stop diseases. In addition most of the herbs used are no longer available. Some diseases like tick-transmitted meningitis are infectious diseases that can be influenced by climate change. Also extreme weather events are known to facilitate some cardiovascular disease like asthma.

ADAPTATION STRATEGIES

Adaptation refers to adjustments in practices, processes or structures in response to projected or actual changes in climate (Dixon, 2003), with the goal of maintaining the capacity to deal with current and future changes. Adaptation to climate change also refers to activities that reduce the negative impacts of climate change and/or takes advantage of new opportunities that may be presented. It includes activities that are taken before impacts are observed (anticipatory) and after impacts have been felt (reactive). Eboh (2009) stated that even if efforts to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are successful, it is no longer possible to avoid some degree of global warming and climate change. This is supported by Francesco (2008) which stated that as a result of greenhouse gases already in the atmosphere from past and current emissions, our planet is already committed to at least as much warming over the 21st century as it has experienced over the 20th century (0.75^{oc}). This implies that in addition to mitigation practices being developed to combat climate change, adaptation to the anticipated climate change is essential. This fact is also made more explicit in Ozor & Cynthia (2010) which stated that while mitigation is necessary to reduce the rate and magnitude of climate change, adaptation is essential to reduce the damages from climate change that cannot be avoided. The Nigerian Agricultural sector in the 21st century will therefore be facing dual significant challenges, arising from the need to increase the nation's food supply as well as adjusting to variation in climate. Also the fact that Agriculture is practiced across a broad range of climates and environmental conditions makes it necessary for the country to develop an array of adaptation options that will meet the different conditions of the different ecological locations of the nation. There are two basic types of adaptation; planned adaptation and autonomous adaptation. Autonomous adaptation refers to reaction of farmers

to changing precipitation patterns, in that he/she changes crops, uses different harvest and planting/sowing dates while planned adaptation measures are conscious policy options or response strategies, often multi-sectorial in nature and aimed at altering the adaptive capacity of the agricultural system of facilitating specific adaptations. A lot of adaptation options have been tried on the different areas of agriculture. Some yielded positive results while the effects of the rest are still being observed. Some of the generally used adaptation options include;

In livestock management, the common adaptation strategies employed by producers include; modifying the time of grazing; altering forage and animal species/breeds; altering the integration within mixed livestock and crop systems including the use of adapted forage crops; ensuring adequate water supplies and the using supplementary feeds and concentrate.

In crop production, a lot of cropping options are also available, these include: altering of the timing or location of cropping activities; improved water management through use of technologies to 'harvest' water, conserve soil moisture (for example, through crop residue retention) and use/transport water more effectively; altering inputs such as crop varieties and species to those with more appropriate thermal time and vernalization; diversifying livelihood strategy to include income from other farming and non farming activities; improving the effectiveness of pest , disease and weed management practices through wider use of integrated pest and pathogen management, development and the use of varieties and species resistant to pests and diseases and maintaining or improving quarantine capabilities and monitoring programs; using climate forecasting tools to reduce production risk.

These adaptation options/strategies must not be used in isolation, farmers can combine two options where necessary in order to achieve the desired result. The fact that Agricultural practices are still climate-sensitive and variations in climate may not be avoided in the nearest future, building up adaptation strategies to cope with the varying climate becomes the most realistic option for farmers to employ in combating climate change risk.

IMPLICATION FOR AGRICULTURAL EXTENSION PRACTICE IN NIGERIA

Agricultural sector is the main stay of many economies in sub-saharan Africa, contributing about 18% of GNP, 23% of the total value of exports and employing 69% of the active labour force. In Nigeria, the roles of agriculture in the economy are: first to provide basic food requirement for the teeming population; second, to contribute to the country's foreign exchange earnings, which in turn provides for the importation of other needed commodities including raw materials; and third, to provide employment to a greater part of the working population; fourth, agriculture serves as a source of local raw materials or industries. Finally, agriculture ensures a high per capita real income for the farmers or arm workers in the rural areas (Nwacukwu, 2003). Over the years the Agricultural sector has not been able to perform these roles effectively due to a lot of factors militating against its practice. Agricultural extension evolved as a result of the pressing need to attend to the information needs of the farmers and agricultural extension work involves disseminating information on agricultural technologies and improved practices to farm families and ensuring farmers' capacity building through the use of a variety of communication methods and training programmes. Hawkins (1998) stated that the major role of agricultural extension in many countries in the past was seen to be transfer of new technologies from researchers to farmers. Agricultural Extension has the mandate of transforming rural communities and farmers through dissemination of information that will improve or change their standard of living. With the emerging significant threat posed by climate change, the agricultural extension system in the country will need to address the following issues in order to overcome the militating effect of climate;

First is the issue of creating awareness on issues of climate change- its effects and adaptation options available to farmers. Studies have shown that the level of awareness on issues of climate change is still low (Nzeadibe et. al. 2010 and Nzeh & Eboh 2010). There is a need for massive awareness to be created in all regions of the country on issues concerning climate change. This will in no small measure help farmers to be alert as well equip themselves to combat issues of climate change. This calls for a review of the communication system in the agricultural system.

Secondly, extension agents, policy makers and researchers in trying to get farmers to adapt to climate change should always involve the farmers and learn from the adaptive measures they are already practicing. This will in no doubt make the adaptation process crisis-free for farmers.

Thirdly, there is a need for change and expansion in the capacity and role of extension agents. Extension agents as well as the entire staff of extension service need to be trained on issues of climate change. This will no doubt help them acquire the needed knowledge that will enable them help farmers and rural people to adapt to the variations in climate. In-depth knowledge of climate change, its effect and adaptation strategies relevant and available for farmers and rural people need to be well understood by the extensionists in order to be able to help the farmers and rural people adapt to the changing climate situation. Technologies that help the farmers/rural dwellers mitigate as well as adapt to climate change need to be identified and brought to their knowledge. Pests and disease resistant crop and animal species need to be also identified and brought to their knowledge.

Fourthly, human activities have tended to exacerbate climate change and its impacts on agriculture and livelihoods in Nigeria. For example, the Niger Delta region of Nigeria is reported to have over 123 gas flaring sites making Nigeria one of the highest emitters of greenhouse gases in Africa (Akinro et. al.2008). A recent study by the World Bank (2008) revealed that Nigeria accounts for roughly one-sixth of worldwide gas flaring. Nigeria flares about 75% of her gas. The flares have apparently contributed more greenhouse gases hence climate change. The country therefore need to reinforce its ban on gas flaring which is suppose to take effect this year, ways of channeling these gases to a useful end need to be identified and utilized.

Fourthly, the curriculum of the agricultural students in tertiary institutions needs to be re-visited and expanded to accommodate issues of climate change. Also research processes and agenda should be influenced to address climate change adaptation and mitigation. The threat posed by climate change if neglected will no doubt render the goal of achieving stable food production in the country unattainable.

Finally, there is a need to encourage creation of linkages and development of partnerships between the government and other actors in climate change issues.

In every counterfeit there is an original, in as much as climate change poses varieties of risks to the food production in the country; there may be some underlying opportunities if the issue is critically examined. Though increase in temperature is generally seen to be destructive to the production of crops and human lives, FAO (2009) noted that livestock production could be boosted by temperature increase. It is now left for the agricultural system to identify those species of both crops and animals that are boosted by those weather situation associated with change in climate.

The expected expansion in the dimension and role of extension system calls for more hands on the desk. This may create room for the unemployed to be employed. Also climate change issues arouse renewed interest in agriculture and if properly channelled will result in greater production.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Recent projections on climate change have shown that global warming will continue in centuries ahead even if emissions of green house gases and aerosol concentration stabilize by maintaining year 2000 levels (IPCC 2007). This implies that predicted impacts of climate change mentioned earlier will intensify above previous expectations.

Agricultural Extension in her bid to improve food production and overall standard of living of the rural populace has faced a myriad of problems among which climate change is very outstanding. For Agricultural Extension to achieve its objective there is an urgent need for the extension system to rise up to this challenge. Extension agents need to be well groomed in issues of climate change, adaptation strategies relevant to the farmer's particular environment need to be available to the farmers. Government on her part need to develop policies to back up institutional efforts to combat threats of climate change.

All these amongst other factors if neglected will surely make the efforts of Agricultural extension practice to bring about food security a mirage, as the threat and risk posed by climate change will in no doubt affect the yield and overall productivity of the farmers.

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